

ECHO:

Expanding Concept and Methodology for Human Past Studies in the
Eastern Baltic Countries

Grant Agreement no 101159883

Deliverable 3.1 - Materials from the workshop on implementing and managing international interdisciplinary research

WP3 – Interdisciplinary and international aspects in studies of human past
in Eastern Baltics

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Executive Summary

The workshop was dedicated to implementing and managing international interdisciplinary research, with the primary goal of laying the foundation for successful collaboration in the study of the human past in the Eastern Baltics. The workshop aligns with the Project Objective 2: To develop constructive communication between specialists from natural sciences and humanities by bringing together project partners in Eastern Baltics – the University of Tartu (UTARTU), the University of Latvia (LU), and Vilnius University (VU). The workshop was organised by the University of Copenhagen.

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Workshop Overview and Objectives

The workshop is part of the WP3 (Interdisciplinary and international aspects in studies of human past in Eastern Baltics) and stays in line with its Objectives:

- O3.1 To guide UTARTU and its Baltic partners in international interdisciplinary collaboration.
- O3.2 To build UTARTU capacity to organize multiple types of data for human past studies.
- O3.3 To set up a framework for long-term collaboration between geneticists and humanities scholars in Eastern Baltics

Date, Location and Format

The in-person workshop took place on **10-11 April, 2025**, at the **National Museum of Denmark**, Undervisningslokale U2. It included four presentation sessions, two keynote, two discussion sessions and a “Scientific speed dating activity”.

Participants

Altogether, 22 people attended the workshop (one joined online), of which ten represented Baltic Universities and 12 were lecturers from various research institutions and disciplines (Table 1).

Table 1. Workshop participants.

Attendees		
Name	Affiliation	Field
Miina Norvik	University of Tartu, Estonia	Linguistics
Mari Tõrv	University of Tartu, Estonia	Archaeology
Kristiina Tambets	University of Tartu, Estonia	Archaeogenetics
Lehti Saag	University of Tartu, Estonia	Archaeogenetics
Alena Kushniarevich	University of Tartu, Estonia	Archaeogenetics
Ingrida Domarkienė	Vilnius University, Lithuania	Genetics
Justina Kozakaitė	Vilnius University, Lithuania	Anthropology
Anna Batraga	University of Latvia, Latvia	Bioarchaeology
Iveta Berga-Muižniece	University of Latvia, Latvia	Archaeology
Alise Pokšāne	University of Latvia, Latvia	Archaeogenetics
Lecturers		
Fernando Racimo	Globe Institute, Copenhagen University, Denmark	Molecular Ecology and Evolution
Samantha S. Reiter	National Museum of Denmark, Denmark	Archaeology
Jessie Woodbridge*	Plymouth University, England	Palaeoecology
Mille Gabriel	National Museum of Denmark, Denmark	Anthropology
Eleonore Pape	Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Germany	Archaeology
Victor Lee	Globe Institute, Copenhagen University, Denmark	Molecular Ecology and Evolution
Peter Hyldegård	Formidlingsakademiet and Videnskab.dk	Communication
Enrico Cappellini	Copenhagen University, Denmark	Palaeoproteomics
Kristian Kristiansen	University of Gothenburg, Sweden	Archaeology
Nicola Ialongo	Aarhus University, Denmark	Archaeology
Jan Kolář	Institute of Archaeology, Czechia	Archaeology
Cristina-Irina Tica	Globe Institute, Copenhagen University, Denmark	Palaeoproteomics
*Attended online		

Workshop Programme

(with speaker names, titles and short summaries)

10 April: Full-day workshop

Arrival 10 am (museum's opening time) Meeting place: Entrance to the National Museum

Introduction

10:15-10:20 Orientation (**Samantha S. Reiter**, Nationalmuseet)

10:20-10:25 Welcome (**Fernando Racimo**, Globe Institute, Copenhagen University)

Strategies for publication

10:30-11:00 "Strategies for publishing in an international and interdisciplinary-friendly manner", **Samantha S. Reiter** (Nationalmuseet and BIAD Consortium)

11:00-11:30 "Open science and palaeoecological databases: unlocking the past for a sustainable future", **Jessie Woodbridge** (Plymouth University—NB: this talk was a video presentation)

Open science can transform the way in which research is conducted and allows emerging globally relevant questions about past and present environmental change to be addressed. Publicly accessible databases of environmental data combined with open science policies foster research transparency and collaboration. Large databases of palaeoecological data have been central to the progression of long-term ecological research in recent decades. For example, the European Pollen Database, a freely accessible repository of fossil pollen records from lake sediments, peat bogs and marine sediments, was established in the early 90s to provide an open platform to support the

This paper will present a series of recommendations for the publication of archaeological data to facilitate efficient databasing with an eye towards international interdisciplinary research. We also include data harmonisation vocabularies utilised for the integration of data from different recording systems. Starting from some case studies from published literature that we present, these recommendations initiate a move towards creating a unified and integrated framework for all types of archaeological data to ultimately sit within a single relational structure.

Study of long-term palaeoecological records to address questions related to biogeography, vegetation history, and ecosystem conservation. The Neotoma database, established in the late 2000s, was created to integrate and manage global datasets related to paleoecology, including microfossils, macrofossils, charcoal, geochemistry, and other environmental records. As a user of these

databases, in this talk I will discuss key outcomes of utilizing records stored in these repositories, some of the challenges of database use and contribution and will highlight areas for advancement in the future, such as via linking with other databases and new collaborations. Data integration, standardisation and quality, contributor recognition, technical issues, community engagement, and sustainable funding are some of the challenges faced. Despite these challenges, scientific community driven databases not only advance knowledge, but also contribute to global efforts towards addressing environmental change.

11:30-12:00 “Knowledge sharing, co-creation and the inclusion of indigenous perspectives in research and research dissemination”, **Mille Gabriel** (Nationalmuseet)

With their roots in a colonial past and their present in a still questionably colonial context, ethnographic collections could today be considered a burden to museums. But colonial collections constitute a unique opportunity for researchers and curators to support the revitalization of traditional knowledge, skills, and know-how by providing tangible, hands-on connections to originating communities. Engaging with originating communities through the sharing of perspectives and knowledge across knowledge mediums, can generate dialectics that have the potential to contribute valuable insights that benefit academic pursuits as well as the dissemination of knowledge and cultural diversity through the museum as a venue. This presentation will focus on my own recent collections-based collaborations with Indigenous partners from the Navajo of the American Southwest, the Tlingit of southeast Alaska, and the Tupinambá peoples northeastern Brazil.

12:00-12:45 LUNCH

12:45-13:15 “Shifts and Challenges in Interdisciplinary Publishing”, **Eleonore Pape** et al. (MP Jena)

The way we author and publish studies on the human past reflects the nature of interdisciplinary collaboration. Archaeogenetics has disrupted traditional practices by shifting publishing formats and authorship conventions: scientific contributions now take center stage, while archaeological contexts are often relegated to supplementary materials. This talk explores challenges in crediting contributions, presenting interdisciplinary research coherently, and effectively utilizing its outputs. While standardized solutions may be unlikely, raising awareness and fostering discussions on authorship and publication practices are key to a more balanced approach.

13:15-13:45 “Genetic Data Integration on BIAD and the development of aDNA metadata standards”, **Victor Lee** (Globe Institute of Copenhagen University)

The growing number of ancient DNA (aDNA) data has provided new opportunities to understand our past but also imposed challenges for data recording and sharing. In this talk, I will demonstrate how aDNA data are being integrated into the Big Interdisciplinary Archaeological Database (BIAD), discuss some challenges and potential solutions, and introduce the Minimum Information about any Ancient Sequence (MIInAS) project on metadata standard development in the aDNA community.

Communication strategies

13:45-14:45 KEYNOTE "Top Ten Lessons Learned from Formidlingsakademiet", **Peter Hyldegård** (Formidlingsakademiet and Videnskab.dk)

14:45-15:30 "Scientific speed dating activity" and COFFEE BREAK

Interdisciplinary research: innovative trends and future

15:30-16:00 "Palaeoproteomics for cultural heritage", **Enrico Cappellini** (Copenhagen University)

Palaeoproteomics, the study of ancient proteins, has emerged as a transformative tool in the field of cultural heritage. This presentation explores the innovative applications of palaeoproteomics in the analysis, preservation, and understanding of cultural heritage artifacts. By leveraging advanced mass spectrometry techniques, researchers can extract and analyze proteins from a variety of historical materials, including bones, teeth, parchments, and textiles. This presentation will highlight key case studies where palaeoproteomics has been successfully applied to cultural heritage, demonstrating its potential to revolutionize the field. By integrating biochemical analysis with archaeological and historical research, palaeoproteomics not only enhances our knowledge of the past but also ensures the protection and longevity of our cultural heritage for future generations.

16:00-16:45 KEYNOTE "Interdisciplinary research past and future" **Kristian Kristiansen** (Univ. Gothenburg)

16:45-17 Wrap up discussion (Chaired by Kristian Kristiansen)

11th April Half-day workshop

9:00 Arrival Nationalmuseet's Personaleindgang (Fredrikholms Canal)

New ways forward - Case studies

9:15-9:45 "Where are all the data (and why aren't we using them)?" **Nicola Ialongo** (Aarhus University)

Prehistoric archaeology has expanded to incorporate more disciplines than one can readily list. Each of these fields—both traditional and emerging—generates and relies on data. Yet, despite this ever-growing wealth of information, we continue to prioritize producing new data over systematically collecting, integrating, and making use of what already exists. Why is this the case? In this talk, I will raise questions for which I have no clear answers—questions that rarely get discussed, but perhaps should be.

9:45-10:15 “Human past from the perspective of interdisciplinary data,” **Jan Kolář** (Institute of Archaeology, Czech Academy of Sciences)

Palaeoecology is therefore one of the closest research allies of archaeology in understanding the role of humans in changing environments. The collaboration between archaeology and other disciplines has a long-standing history. Especially after founding of the IPCC in 1988 with the global awakening due to the upcoming significant impact of climate changes, the need of knowing how people interacted with their environment in the deep past became apparent. Archaeology has a big advantage of shared time scale with palaeoecology. This is valid especially for the Holocene, for which both disciplines have rich datasets which can be analysed on national, continental or even global level. The key advancements of the future lie in archaeological data and what we do with it. We need to exploit fully the richness of not only the most straightforward lines of evidence (e.g., eDNA, lipids, environmental archaeology, radiocarbon dates), but crucial is also the rich cultural data, into which archaeologists put vast amounts of energy during the last 120 years. This paper will revise the current approaches of coupling the diverse strand of scientific data on the past of human-environment interactions, offer successful case studies from Central Europe and discuss the future directions of interdisciplinary research, from both theoretical and methodological perspectives.

10:15-10:35 COFFEE BREAK

10:35-11:00 “A transdisciplinary study of childhood health east of the *limes*”, **Cristina-Irina Tica** (Globe Institute, Copenhagen University)

The study of childhood health in the past has recently experienced an increased interest in the science community, although the emphasis has still very much been on the Western sphere and on the Roman Empire. Hoping to rectify this trend in childhood paleopathology, the current investigation shifts the lens of interrogation from the Roman Empire to its edges, and from gentes and provincials to the ‘*barbarians*’ outside their borders, to get a better understanding of health and disease in children from communities east of the Roman *limes*. One of the main objectives of this project is to investigate whether there were any cultural and biological differences between male and female children from Sarmatian communities living on the Great Hungarian Plain. However, working with archaeological skeletal remains of pre-pubertal individuals makes osteological sex estimations based on morphological techniques very unreliable and problematic;

therefore, we used a streamlined mass spectrometry-based workflow for the estimation of sex using targeted amelogenin (AMELX/AMELY) peptides from dental enamel by employing a minimally invasive sampling strategy via acid etching and high-resolution liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry using parallel reaction monitoring assay. As such, the aims of this project are realized by integrating methods from bioarchaeology and paleoproteomics, and facilitated by an international collaborative network.

11-11:45 Closing discussion

11:45-12:15 Highlights of the prehistoric collections; National Museum of Denmark (<https://en.natmus.dk/>)

Workshop content and materials

Key highlights and discussion points from the workshop sessions.

Strategies for publication

- I. Problems and recommendations for the publication of archaeological data to improve their usability.

Problem: Archaeological data have always been incomplete and biased, shaped by cultural, taphonomic, regional, and practical factors, as well as varying publication and archiving practices (Reiter et al., 2025 and references therein).

Solution: To adhere standards in databasing and publishing. Big Interdisciplinary Archaeological Database (BIAD) (<https://biadwiki.org/>) represents a practical example of construction of a big database following the developed standards (BIAD standards) that aim at increasing the usability, visibility, interoperability, and longevity of data as well as facilitating an integration of natural sciences and archaeological research.

BIAD standards (Reiter et al., 2025):

- securely positioning data in space and time
- referencing data sources
- consistently harmonising data outcomes
- reporting results comprehensively
- describing data fully
- common vocabularies

Problem: integration of genetic and archaeological data, lack of standards in ancient DNA metadata reports.

Solution: standard and community-agreed-upon sample, library, and sequencing metadata checklists for ancient DNA studies. Introduction of *The **Minimum Information about any Ancient Sequence*** (MInAS) project (<https://www.mixs-minas.org/>). Introduction of the BIAD checklists of reporting archaeological data in archaeogenomic studies (Staniuk et al., in preparation).

II. Open science and palaeoecological databases: unlocking the past for a sustainable future.

The talk highlighted existing open-access palaeoecological databases as well as some challenges one faces when using them (data integration, standardisation and quality, contributor recognition, community engagement). Several examples of successful data integration from various databases (e. g biodiversity and land use change in the British Isles (Woodbridge et al., 2023)) and suggestions for future directions (interdisciplinarity and synergy in addressing research questions, better integration of different databases, AI use for data mining) were inspiring.

III. Shifts and Challenges in Interdisciplinary Publishing

Problem: Natural and humanities sciences had traditionally different publication standards. Archaeogenetics studies that bring together the two fields revealed the need to reconsider the approaches of how archaeological and genetic data are integrated in the publication, as well as in authorship practices.

Action: Eleonore Pape is currently working on the manuscript that addresses challenges in co-authorship in archaeogenetic studies and invites other research groups, especially those from archaeogenetics, to contribute to it.

Communication strategies

We discussed some key aspects of communicating science to the public (formulating goals of communication; channels; communicating facts vs presenter's opinion, etc.).

Interdisciplinary research: innovative trends and future

I. Interdisciplinary research: past and future

Problem: Integration of advanced scientific methods from natural sciences (genetics, isotopic analysis, and proteomics) into archaeological research had a transformative impact on the latter:

- Enhanced interdisciplinary collaboration
- Shifted archaeology toward big data and large-scale comparisons
- Raised ethical questions (data ownership, indigenous rights, and the interpretation of bioarchaeological evidence).

Some challenges in interdisciplinarity (archaeology-genetics) formulated by Kristian Kristiansen in 2022, and where are we now (excerpt from the lecture):

1. Sampling and collaborative ethics. This topic has risen to become a key issue, with papers discussing the demands that need to be fulfilled. How do we create a truly integrated collaborative sampling and project design. *Progress has been made and more to come*

2. Lost in translation: terminologies and contexts. What is in a word (terminology), and what is in a context? I propose that the answer to those questions demands a discussion of how archaeological contexts relate to the formation of culture, and the ways we label and interpret culture. *Still to be developed*

3. Big Data: towards open access. How do we create open access archaeological databases to match those of aDNA? To be able to reproduce and re-use existing Big Data is a prerequisite for advancing archaeological data analysis to new levels, and to further advance interdisciplinarity. *On its way, takes time*

4. From interdisciplinarity to transdisciplinarity. Liv Nilsson Stutz suggests that to create a more productive environment for interdisciplinary collaboration, it is necessary to understand what it takes and that it represents a demanding process of increasing knowledge-sharing. *Not there yet, demands new teaching courses in archaeology, linguistics and perhaps other disciplines*

5. Genes versus culture. This field of research is theoretically the most demanding and therefore also contested. I propose two themes for further examination: 1. How do genetic admixture processes relate to cultural admixture processes? 2. How do we translate biological mating processes into rules of kinship and marriage? *A few case studies, but still a long way to go. Would also demand new teaching courses in kinship analysis*

II. Palaeoproteomics

Key highlights: Palaeoproteomics – study of ancient proteins - is powerful method in evolutionary and cultural heritage research; it is an interdisciplinary field - combines biochemical analysis with archaeological and historical data; sources of material – bones, teethes, parchments, textile; main method is mass spectrometry; challenges – damage, contamination, limited amount of material.

We also discussed a case of studying childhood health from the Sarmatian period in Central Europe using bioarchaeology and palaeoproteomics. Importantly, it demonstrated benefits of using mass spectrometry-based sex estimation from dental enamel proteins, which is less invasive and more reliable as compared to traditional osteological methods, especially when applied to sexing of pre-pubertal individuals.

New ways forward - Case studies

I. Archaeology: where are all the data (and why aren't we using them)?

Problem: In interdisciplinary research, the value that archaeology can bring is much more than just context, interpretation, and narrative.

In their case study on Bronze Age economics in Europe (Ialongo and Lago, 2024), the authors demonstrated that, when transparent and reproducible, archaeological data provides quantitative information suitable for statistical analysis and simulation, like methods used in the natural sciences.

II. Human past from the perspective of interdisciplinary data.

Problem: An inter- (or transdisciplinary) approach is important when studying the human past.

On the example of human-vegetation interactions in the past using data from two disciplines - palaeoecology (pollen records) and archaeology (radiocarbon dates) (Macek et al., 2022) - we discussed challenges and potential of such a frame of interdisciplinarity. These included different scientific traditions but overlapping time scale and long-standing interaction of archaeology with related sciences, respectively; the importance of study design as the very first step of an interdisciplinary project; and the importance of data integration.

Workshop Outputs

I. Participants from UTARTU, LU, and VU shared their experience on the status of the interdisciplinary research in archaeogenetic studies in their institutions.

UTARTU: Geneticists have long-term collaboration with archaeologists and linguists in Estonia through the Collegium for Transdisciplinary Studies in Archaeology, Genetics and Linguistics, University of Tartu (https://www.aql.ut.ee/?page_id=472&lang=en). This collaboration is reflected in completed and currently running interdisciplinary projects as well as in the consortium of the Centre of Excellence for Transdisciplinary Studies on Ethnogenesis and Cultural diversity Estonian Roots (01.01.2024–31.12.2030) (<https://www.etis.ee/portal/projects/display/0b4c458c-c64f-401c-914f-d84f33d25cad>)).

VU has established collaboration between archaeologists and geneticists, whereas members from LU reported a rather low level of communication between experts of different disciplines or even groups.

Within the ECHO project, we aim to enhance interdisciplinary dialogue between humanities and natural science experts of the Eastern Baltic region. Highlights from the workshop, mapped challenges in the interdisciplinary research, and proposed solutions on how to overcome them helped to bring the experts from Eastern Baltics to “the same page” and served as a good background to further developments.

II. Archaeologists from UTARTU acknowledged the problem of the existence of multiple databases even within one country and the current low level of integration of data between them.

III. Lecturers shared their presentations along with related articles and books thereby creating a workshop material collection on interdisciplinary and international research that can be used further.

IV. Important outcome of the workshop was getting to know various experts from different disciplines, supported also by the Scientific speed dating activity.

Conclusions and Follow-up

- The workshop structure and materials will serve both as an inspiration and help for the preparation of the “Staff course on interdisciplinarity and international collaboration” within WP3 of the ECHO project.
- Attendance of the workshop by the experts from the Eastern Baltic universities (UTARTU, LU, and VU) creates a favourable background for further developments of an interdisciplinary and international research network in the region planned within the ECHO project. The workshop ideas will help in developing a long-term collaboration strategy for Eastern Baltic research institutions.
- An important follow-up of the workshop will be guidance on organizing and harmonizing multiple types of data for human past studies by Experts from BIAD consortium (<https://biadwiki.org/>) for experts from UTARTU, LU, and VU (WP3). A dedicated workshop takes place in Tartu on June 4-5, 2025, where 11 experts from the Eastern Baltic Institutions will get an introduction to BIAD as well as to principles of data integration into large databases. The course will be led by five experts from BIAD consortium.

References

BIAD: Big Interdisciplinary Archaeological Database (<https://biadwiki.org/>)

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